

VISS

First report on public engagement actions/D7.4

WP7, T7.3

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1. Abbreviations List

CE	Circular Economy
CSO	Civil Society Organisations
Dn.n	Deliverable number
DoA	Description of Action
IAP2	International Association of Public Participation
Mn	Month of the project
OI	Open Innovation
PHBV	Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
R+D	Research and Development
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SRL	Social Readiness Level
Tn.n	Task number
WPn	Work package number

2. Objectives and scope

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.4 *First Report on Public Engagement Actions* and is a summary of activities that have been performed by the ViSS project within task 7.3 *Public engagement*, until Month 18. This activity is framed within ViSS WP7 *ViSS outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity building* and therefore, the engagement activities complement the ViSS First Report on dissemination and communication (D7.3).

This document **updates the Public Engagement strategy (D7.2)** launched in M9 and will be completed on M33 (D7.9; *Second report on public engagement action*; May 2026), and on M48 (D7.15 *Final public engagement actions*; August 2027). The lessons learnt during the public engagement activities will be applied in other tasks such as T7.4 (Networking and Clustering) and T7.5 (Open Innovation and capacity building).

The **objective** of the public engagement strategy in ViSS is **to involve the relevant stakeholders for participating in the SRL assessment to be carried out in WP6 (T6.4), to enhance the acceptability of ViSS results and solutions, support the social change processes and increasing awareness, and to support communication & dissemination activities.**

Therefore, the **aim** of D7.4 is **to inform on the undertaken activities and present modification of the initial design of the conceptual framework for public engagement and the ecosystem analysis** presented in D7.2 (Section 3), as well as the initial diagnosis (Section 3) will be reminded providing updates from the initial plan. Furthermore, the undertaken activities and the Action Plan (Section 4) are presented with insight on future public engagement actions activities.

3. Introduction: Public engagement processes and Ecosystem analysis

ViSS public engagement strategy relies on the **Quintuple Helix of Stakeholders** model [1] for the public participation. It is understood as collaborative knowledge generation involving relevant stakeholders for participating in the definition of the Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework (SSbD) and the SRL (Social Readiness Level) assessment that will take place in WP6, but it also plays a key role enhancing acceptability of the ViSS products, solutions and value chain and supporting the social change processes and increasing awareness required for the transition towards a circular economy, thus supporting the dissemination and communication strategy.

ViSS Public Engagement strategy is committed to **the IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation** [2], which will contribute to identifying those aspects of public participation which cross national, cultural, and religious boundaries, and help make better decisions which reflect the interests and concerns of potentially affected stakeholders (please read D7.2 for further information and Figure 1).

Figure 1: IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation

The ViSS public engagement strategy is deployed following a four-step process developed in depth in D7.2: Ecosystem analysis, Diagnosis, Action Plan and Dissemination and Communication. This document will be focused on the steps that have been updated:

- **Ecosystem analysis:** In D7.2, information was gathered on existing resources for public participation in the region of Murcia and the province of Alicante, both in terms of relevant infrastructure and stakeholders. The stakeholders were included in the Annex. Since the publication of D7.2 to the launch of this deliverable, the stakeholders’ database has been updated in the project internal repository by the partners, in the form of an excel spreadsheet.

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-**Diagnosis:** This step has been updated in Section 3 of this deliverable, selecting existing infrastructures (both face to face and virtual) that will be used for the ViSS project and dismissing others that have not revealed usable or accessible, and further defining recommendations according to the level of participation required in the Action Plan, to determine the infrastructures that must be designed.

- **Action Plan and undertaken activities:** Based on the ecosystem analysis implemented for D7.2 and the revision of the diagnosis step, this section first reviews the Public Engagement activities that have been undertaken until March 2025 (M18 of the project) and subsequently updates the action-oriented timeline with the reorganisation of concrete activities, distributed according to the partners' expertise and responsibilities and the status of the project developments.

- **Dissemination and Communication:** The activities undertaken have been reported in the First report on Dissemination and Communication (D7.3).

4. Diagnosis

The Citizen Engagement Infrastructures (virtual and face to face) are developed in D7.2. After the analysis of the existing virtual and face-to-face infrastructures in the previous section, **the following have been selected as they are relevant to the scope of the ViSS project and topics** (Circular Economy, Biobased plastic, Environmental Management). **Participation will be promoted through information about ViSS activities and results, and promoting consultations and activities related to circular economy such as surveys, talks, and encouraging public debate on the topics of the project.**

In the first year and a half of the project only the Fundación Seneca infrastructure has been used as ViSS project was present in Murcia Science Week where CETEC and CETBIO could present the project to more than 1000 persons (see Section 5.1.1.1). The project was also presented by the University of Alicante in the Researchers’ Night (see Section 5.1.1.2). Table 1 presents the virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation effectively used so far by ViSS project, in dark blue. On the contrary, the infrastructures in grey have been discarded, being out of the scope of the project and not accessible to promote activities: the Participation Platforms set up in the Region of Murcia and the Community of Valencia, and the Regional Advisory Councils in both regions.

Table 1: Virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation at regional and local level

Type	Murcia	Alicante
Virtual	Fundación Seneca ¹ Region of Murcia Participation Platform	UA Volunteer Website ² Community of Valencia Participation Platform
Face-to-face	Murcia Science Week ³ Regional Environmental Assessment Council	Regional Advisory and Participatory Council in Environment (CAPMA) University of Alicante Researchers’ Night ⁴

Moreover, **key alliances are being identified based on the analysis of the key stakeholders. Questionnaires** will be used along the project implementation aimed at the different stakeholders to visualise the degree of affinity with the project objectives and their power to influence in this context. A preliminary analysis based on previous related projects resulted in the development of a SWOT matrix (presented in D7.2) for engagement processes in the field of bioplastics and circular economy.

¹ <https://fseneca.es/>

² <https://web.ua.es/es/voluntariado-ua/voluntariado-medioambiental/voluntariado-medioambiental.html>

³ <https://fseneca.es/web/xxi-semana-de-la-ciencia-y-la-tecnologia-de-la-region-de-murcia>
<https://fseneca.es/web/la-semana-de-la-ciencia-se-acerca-a-las-400-actividades>

⁴ <https://www.informacion.es/universidad/ua/2024/09/16/european-researchers-night-nit-investigacio-108200583.html>

4.1 Levels of participation in ViSS activities

VISS foresees **engagement processes through activities carried out in the Region of Murcia and the province of Alicante**, as well as at EU level, that entail different levels of participation, based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* (developed in D7.2).

The spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high participation, where they are empowered to take the final decision on the issue at hand (i.e., through deliberative forums or referendums)[3].

The spectrum levels within the ViSS project are applied as follows (developed in D7.2 at higher detail):

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed and will acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will seek direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions from you. Your advice and recommendations will be incorporated into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

Citizen engagement goal: To place final decision-making in the public

Promise to the public: We will implement what you decide.

4.2 ViSS Participation Infrastructure

In addition to the already existing participation infrastructures mentioned in section 3.1, the following virtual channels and sites are used for the VISS public engagement:

- **Web platform:** ViSS website (<https://viss-project.eu/>) – active, managed by ICONS as WP7 leader. The website homepage includes information on the project, resources to download (deliverables, flyer, postcard), and news at EU level.
- **Social networks:** The [LinkedIn](#) profile has been accompanied since November 2024 by a [Facebook page](#), aimed at raising awareness about **biodegradable materials for food packaging** and developing a **circular value chain** and publishing updates and activities undertaken in the project.

Moreover, the project is present face-to-face through:

- **Science Week** held in Murcia each year, where information on the advances is distributed among visitors, and they are involved in small experiments at the CETEC booth that showcase the processes developed in the project.
- **The volunteer service of University of Alicante:** provides information on the Citizen Science activity carried by the partner UA and facilitates logistical support to the recruitment of volunteers (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Volunteer service University of Alicante

5. Undertaken activities and Action Plan

According to the diagnosis, the following engagement activities are planned within ViSS under the different levels of Engagement. In this section, a list of activities suitable for each level of participation is proposed. Nevertheless, it must be taken into consideration that the Action Plan is dynamic, and it will be updated in a collaborative manner, with contributions from all partners.

5.1.1 Information level

- *Short videoclips*

As stated in the First Dissemination and Communication report (D7.3), a series of 14 short video-interviews have been recorded with several project partners (TCA, VIDAL, IRIS, CETBIO, VTT, BHAM, CETEC, HELIAN, AITEX, PROPAGROUP, BEAULIEU, KVC, IDENER, UA) on the different steps involved in the creation of sustainable and recyclable food packaging. In addition, 4 videos were released in a campaign implemented with other EU projects, such as Agro2circular or researchers, related to plastic packaging. More information is available in D7.3. Hence, this activity has been completed.

5.1.1.1 Science week.

During the weekend between 25th and 27th October 2024, CETBIO attended the Technological Centres booth of the **Science Week** organised by Fundación Séneca in Murcia. The partners presented the ViSS project to civil society, being the public mostly families and groups from educational centres and showcased the biotechnological processes for PHBV production that are being developed within the project. More than **1000 participants** visited the stand and were informed about the project advances (data provided by the promoters of the Science Week event. Most attendees were students, more information at this link <https://fseneca.es/secyt24/>).

Figure 3: CETBIO stand at the Science Week in Murcia

5.1.1.2 EU Researchers' night (UA):

UA has participated with a stand in **two researchers' nights in Alicante**: the 2023 edition held on 29th September 2023 (more info in [Link](#)), where they raised awareness about the impact of plastic contamination in Mediterranean beaches, and the ViSS solutions aiming to address plastic pollution through the development of biodegradable and biosourced materials. There were around **12000 visitors** to the event (data provided by the promoters of the researchers' night).

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Figure 4: Researchers' nights in Alicante

At the 2024 edition, that took place at University of Alicante on 27 September, the research group at UA, the Bioplastic Láb, also installed a stand, "Plastic contamination in our beaches" in which the results of the Citizen Science activities were shown to more than **14000 visitors** (data provided by the promoters of the researchers' night), mostly families and students (more info in [this link](#)).

5.1.1.3 Talks and seminars for youngsters

KVC has performed a **literature review for educational materials** that can be adapted for talks and seminars aimed at youngsters in primary and secondary schools and higher education institutions. These talks will be offered to educational centres and youth associations, including those already mapped in D7.2 and additional actors detected during the project activities, through brochures and tailored emails. Up to date, a meeting was held with teaching staff at the Engineering School of UPV, where possibilities to align ViSS topics with the existing curricula were explored.

Slideshows on the SSbD assessment have already been created (reported in D7.5: First report on capacity building resources and actions) to be used in Capacity Building activities. Contents are being currently adapted to other target groups.

5.1.2 Involvement level

5.1.2.1 Beach cleaning (University of Alicante - UA)

UA has undertaken three beach cleaning activities in the first 18 months of the project.

The first activity took place in Agua Amarga beach on 2nd February 2024 (Figure 4), close to Alicante city, where 40 volunteers recruited with the collaboration of the volunteering service of University of Alicante cleaned a section of 200 m, while classifying the litter found using the list facilitated by EU Marine Litter Watch and the protocol and list facilitated by [MARNOPA project](#) (in Spanish), a project supported by the [Ministry of Ecological Transition \(MITECO\)](#).

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Figure 5: Beach cleaning in February 2024, Agua Amarga. Photo: Bioplastic Lab (UA)

The second beach cleaning activity was implemented in Calpe (Alicante) in May 2024 (Figure 5). The activity was accompanied by a booth in which UA explained the problem to the public. 12 participants took part in the cleaning activity.

Figure 6: Beach cleaning in May 2025, Calpe. Photo: Bioplastic Lab (UA)

The third activity took place on 9th November 2024 (Figure 6), in the Agua Amarga beach as the first activity. It counted with the participation of 25 volunteers, most of them degree and master students at UA. During the activity, the participants highlighted the problem with the microplastics, since although the beach looked clean at the beginning, the classification method used revealed a high amount of small plastic pieces were present. This way, the beach cleaning contributed to raise awareness on the problem of plastic pollution in the Mediterranean beaches.

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Figure 7: Beach Cleaning at Agua Amarga, November 2024.

These activities have involved in total 77 people and have been an opportunity for the participants to help collect data on plastic pollution and understand the dimension of this pollution.

5.1.3 Collaboration level

5.1.3.1 Development of SSbD approach (T6.2).

Figure 8: Slide of Mentimeter used for development of SsbD approach. March 2024

Partners were invited to participate in 3 workshops, to define the methodologies and indicators that will be used in the SSbD framework

- The **first workshop** was held during the General Assembly in Valencia (March 2024), where a general approach of the SSbD was presented, with the aim of deciding on the principles and dimensions that should be included in the SSbD framework.

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Mentimeter was used (Figure 7) enabling the participation of those partners attending to the Assembly online. All the dimensions were explored and partners provided feedback on indicators they deemed not relevant or others that may be relevant and missing. The results of the workshop were further discussed among the partners directly involved in the SSbD framework (KVC, IDE, VTT) and the coordinator CETEC.

- The **second workshop was** held during the General Assembly in Seville (October 2024). This workshop was focused on the environmental LCA and led by VTT. Due to the complexity of the value chain involved in the ViSS project, the project aimed at clarifying the different steps included, the technical partners involved in the different processes and the data that would be required for monitoring and assessment, using a spreadsheet to harmonise formats and units.

5.1.4 Empowerment level

Although no activities in ViSS directly address the empower level, it is considered that **this degree of engagement is reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes, which requires as conditions an enhanced awareness** (about the circular economy, the territory and the sectors involved), the acquisition of capacities and knowledge and the generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation, allowing citizens, CSO representatives and policy makers to make informed choices and fight disinformation and “greenwashing”, as well as supporting the inclusion of the project outcomes in regulations and the implementation of policies related to plastic packaging and waste management .

Hence, it is considered that the empowerment level is achieved through ViSS Public Tool embedded in the ICT platform (D6.1, submitted in Month 9, June 2024) developed in Task 6.1 and nurtured with data from the SSbD. Up to date, the Public Tool has experimented a slight delay, related to the early TRL of the products and processes being developed in ViSS projects, and the need to harmonize the data obtained in the different assessments, to offer information that is at the same time accessible and reliable. The public tool is not only aimed at citizens and consumers, but also to CSOs and decision makers, showing real time indicators such as the quantity of sugar wastes collected, quantity of poultry wastes collected, quantity of PHBV produced and other data on the product life cycle and characteristics accessible to end users, allowing them to make sustainable decisions and to formulate relevant sustainability policies and plans according to the data.

5.2 Programmed activities (developed in D7.2):

The programmed activities for Years 2, 3 and 4 will continue as outlined in D7.2. The schedule has been reproduced in the figures for each level.

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5.2.1 Information level:

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
Short videoclips				■	■											
Talks					■	■		■	■	■		■	■	■		
Packaging showcases															■	■
Capacity building actions					■	■		■	■	■		■	■	■		
Events				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■		

5.2.1.1 Talks to youngsters.

After the project materials (slideshows, brochures) have been prepared by KVC in the first months of 2025 (January-March), **an extensive and systematic dissemination and communication campaign will be implemented among educational centres** (primary and secondary school, vocational training) and CSOs (youth associations, environmental associations) of Murcia and Alicante, to engage the teachers interested. **A calendar will be proposed, to deliver more than 10 talks between September and May of the scholar years 2025-2026 and 2026-2027.** The objective of the talks will be to raise awareness on circular economy and bioplastics. UA has also a programme that facilitates visits of students from secondary schools, managed through a specific section of their website (Figure 9) and will receive students next 7th March to explain their research, including the ViSS project.

Figure 9: Section in UA website dedicated to awareness activities.

5.2.1.2 Packaging showcases.

As indicated in the Public Engagement Strategy, **this activity will be performed during the last year of the project**, once the plastic packaging demos are delivered. As VIDAL withdrew as partner due to technical constraints, this partner was replaced by other sweet industry in the region of Murcia

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(ZUKAN) who will be responsible for implementing more than 4 four packaging showcases for consumers in supermarkets and candy shops, aimed at increasing awareness among consumers on sustainable packaging. **The project will leverage on special occasions** (Environment Day, New Years’ Day, World Recycling Day) to draw attention of the consumers through booths installed in the supermarkets with graphic arrangements and spreading messages with social content on the topics of the project.

5.2.1.3 Capacity building actions

Activity T7.5 will involve **more than 40 capacity building actions** (workshops, technical seminars, etc) aimed at different sectors on different topics related to ViSS, during the Years 2, 3 and 4 of the project. These activities are planned in detail in D7.5 (First report on Open Innovation and Capacity Building activities, M18, March 2025). At the moment of launching this deliverable, materials are being prepared, including brochures and flyers to offer them to the targeted stakeholders.

5.2.1.4 Participation in external events

Partners will continue taking part on events such as the Science Week Fair organised by Seneca Foundation in Murcia (held every year at the end of October/beginning of November), or **Researchers’ Night** (organised by UA) raising awareness on the challenges of plastic pollution and bioplastic solutions. Also, industry fairs and other events at the EU level are foreseen along the project, in coordination with T7.4 (Networking and clustering) led by TCA.

5.2.2 Consultation level

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
Surveys, questionnaires																

Figure 10: Consultation level.

Consultation activities in ViSS will consist on surveys and questionnaires, framed within different activities of the project are foreseen in several activities of the project (Figure 9):

- In Task 6.4.3, KVC will implement **surveys and questionnaires** along the years 2, 3 and 4 of the project. These will encompass both existing tools and others developed ad hoc for the project, for the socioeconomical analysis of the impact, contributing to offer comprehensive insights on social structures and roles, environmental awareness and acceptability of bio-based products. At the date of launch of this deliverable, KVC is revising the available data and tools, to generate the surveys in a holistic approach, taking into consideration different stakeholder groups (workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers) and indicators linked to the concerned Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The tools and results will be further detailed in D6.7 (First sustainable by design assessment, M18), D6.10 (Interim sustainable by design assessment; M33) and D6.15(Final sustainable by design assessment , M47).

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- In T7.6 post-project exploitation & long-term feasibility, ICONS will perform **surveys and interviews among partners and stakeholders** to explore socio-economic context, markets and users' needs. The tools and results will be reported in D7.8 (Interim Plan of Dissemination, M24) and D7.12 (Final plan of dissemination, communication & exploitation; M36).

5.2.3 Involvement level:

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
Citizen science initiatives																
Contests and prizes																
Delphi groups for SSbD																

Figure 11: Involvement level

5.2.3.1 Citizen science initiatives

5 further activities are planned by UA and the data will be uploaded to the **Marine Litter Watch** from EU environment Agency) and **MARNOBA database by Vertidos Cero Association** in collaboration with the **Ministry of Climate Change and Demographical Challenge (MITERD)**. Further collaborations with civil society organisations will be sought, to raise awareness on the problem of plastic litter in oceans.

5.2.3.2 Contests and prizes

KVC will organise more than six contests aimed at consumers and general public, related to solving problems related to circularity and end-of-life routes of bio-based plastics, to foster the sustainable attitudes and behaviours and to increase the acceptance of the biobased products. This activity can be organised in a complementary way to other actions, such as the talks and seminars planned for youngsters, and citizen science activities, and coincide with relevant dates for environmental protection (Oceans' Day, Environment's Day, Recycling Date, etc). The contests will be planned for the years 2,3 and 4 (at least two contest per year) and regional schools and high schools will be engaged, together with consumers and neighbour associations.

5.2.3.3 Delphi group for SSbD

A 2-round Delphi process was initially planned to contribute to the definition of the SSbD framework (T6.2), differentiating two groups

- Group 1 focused on safety, environmental & economic sustainability of bio-based plastics (led by IDE)
- Group 2 focused on social readiness for bio-based plastics (led by KVC)

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Nevertheless, the process revealed that the TRL of the ViSS solution was not sufficient mature, and some dimensions of SSbD (particularly the social pillar) require further advances to be harmonised with the safety and environmental issues. Hence, the Delphi group has been repurposed for the last two years of the project, in which ViSS technologies will reach higher degrees of TRL, to develop recommendations for improvement of the SSbD framework and for the widespread adoption in industry. The expert group will be conformed based on the networks of the partners, but also leveraging on existing platforms of experts in the SSbD methodology such as the created by the European Commission on SSbD, with the areas of knowledge described in Table 2. Moreover, the expert group will support the innovation and co-creation processes across the ViSS transdisciplinary actions, and the monitoring and evaluation of ViSS results through nonbiased views, in face to face and online events.

Table 2: Expertise of the expert group

Safety-risk assessment	Environmental & sustainability impact
Social impact.	Circular bioeconomy
Consumers’ representative.	Decision making.
Recyclers’ representative.	Industrial end-users’ representatives.

5.2.4 Collaboration level:

Collaboration activities within ViSS are performed mainly within the consortium

Figure 12: Collaboration level.

5.2.4.1 SSbD assessment activities

Collaborative workshops will be organised among the partners for the monitoring and evaluation of the results considering environmental, economic and social dimensions, particularly those referring to workers and value chain. Firstly, the baseline has been assessed during the last quarter of 2024 and the results have been reported in D6.7 (M18, March 2025). Subsequently, more than 13 additional workshops will be organised along 2025, 2026 and 2027, to perform the interim assessment (reported in D6.10; M33) and the final assessment (D6.15; M47). For those workshops, partners will be divided into 2 groups,

- Group 1 led by KVC for the social readiness assessment involving consumers, decision makers, industry and research communities

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- Group 2 led by IRIS, CETEC & AITEX with industrial/recycling sectors and decision makers in charge of waste management schemes aimed to gaining common insights in further management schemes for biodegradable plastic products, including their sorting.

5.2.4.2 Round tables and meetings

Will be organised by KVC and IDE during the last semester of 2026 and during 2027, aimed at supporting the implementation of ViSS CEBM (with financial intermediaries) and supporting SSbD and social readiness for bio-based value-chains (decision makers, CSOs, industries). This activity will be coordinated at the regional and local level with the cross-fertilisation activities also planned for Networking and Clustering (T7.4)

5.2.4.3 Cross-fertilisation activities

Cross-fertilisation activities with initiatives and projects will be performed within task 7.4 on networking and clustering led by TCA and CETEC. Some examples of initiatives are those related to residues as feedstocks for biotechnological processes, SSbD approach, social readiness for plastic products, bio-based plastics, recycling & sorting, and governance models for the waste management of bio-based value chains. Cooperation with initiatives **including the Knowledge Centre on Bioeconomy (KCB)**, Joint Research Centre (JRC) will be sought for sharing methodologies and enabling common approaches. At the date of launch of this deliverable, the partners have been discussing the joint creation of a Stakeholder Community at the EU level, that serve the objectives of tasks 7.2 (EU outreach), 7.3 (Public engagement) and 7.4 (Networking and clustering). Further information on the methods can be found in D7.1. and D7.3 (Networking and clustering section).

5.2.5 Empower level

The next activities at the empowerment level **will be aimed at enhancing the framework conditions for decision making, through the further development of the Public Tool**, being the last progress reported in D6.5 (Second integration and assessment of data in ICT platform, M18; March 2025). Since the public tool is aimed at citizens, CSOs and decision makers, to allow them obtaining real time and real reliable information that facilitates decision making in purchases and policy making, it requires an advanced TRL of the solutions (closer to final products), while preserving the confidentiality of the data as established in the IPR policy. This will imply the organization of meetings with several partners and stakeholders, among them CETEC, KVC, IDE, VTT, ICONS to refine the features contained in the Public Tool and the most adequate interface to ensure user-friendliness, accessibility of data representation, and compatibility to be embedded at the project website. Moreover, meetings will be programmed with partners responsible of technical developments, to delimitate the data that can be offered as supplementary information in the Public Tool, according to IPR requirements.

Secondly, activities aimed at awareness raising and capacity building will be planned, already included in other engagement levels (see [Information Level](#)). In addition, it should be highlighted that KVC and CETEC will perform capacity building actions related to digital tools supporting SSbD & social readiness, targeting not only the industry, but also policy makers & administration and civil society, as described in D7.5 (First report on capacity building resources and actions; M18; March

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2025); the resources elaborated may include tutorials and guidelines for the use of the Public Tool, and the interpretation of results, allowing the extraction of recommendations to formulate relevant sustainable policies and measures.

This task implies the continuous update of data, and further integrations will take place along the project lifecycle, reported in D6.8- Third integration and assessment of data in ICT platform (M33; June 2026) and D6.13 - Final integration and assessment of data in ICT platform (M47; August 2027).

6. Conclusions

The objectives of public engagement in ViSS are:

- to involve the relevant stakeholders for participating in the SRL assessment to be carried out in WP6 (T6.4),
- to enhance the acceptability of ViSS results and solutions,
- to support the social change processes and increasing awareness,
- to support communication & dissemination activities.

The Deliverable 7.2 Public Engagement Strategy of the ViSS project, and the Document of Action (DoA) have been followed to ensure the foreseen objectives and goals allowing the long-term sustainability of ViSS results.

The activities in the engagement activity will be focused to the regional level (Murcia and Alicante) where there is a variety of stakeholders and participation infrastructures to engage society at different levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate). Some of the activities, aimed at awareness raising, will be also implemented in Valencia province to enhance the outreach. The partners leading T7.2 (overall dissemination and communication); T7.3 (public engagement) and T7.4 (Networking and clustering) are currently planning meetings to better coordinate the creation and management of a Stakeholder Community and the activities foreseen, to generate synergies among them.

At the date of delivery of this document, some activities (most related to talks, capacity building and organisation of contests) have been delayed in relation to the initial Public Engagement Strategy Action Plan, due to the lack of maturity of the technologies and solutions being developed by the project.

As well, the set-up of a Stakeholder Panel for SSbD Assessment framework was discarded and replaced with collaboration with the SSbD working group already existing, to avoid duplicities and to ensure that the results are widely accepted and adopted at EU level.

The next steps that will be performed in the next months are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Next steps by participation level

Inform	- Finish educational materials and organise talks and webinars	KVC
	- Start talks and seminars with youngsters: slideshows and materials.	KVC, UA
	- Start capacity building actions: promotional materials	KVC, IDE, UA, TCA, IRIS, CETEC, BHAM, HP
Involve	- Next Citizen Science activity planned in May 2025	UA
	- Organise contests and prizes	KVC
Collaborate	- Cross-fertilisation activities (follow-up)	TCA, CETEC
Empower	- Meetings on Public Tool features (including interface and data representation)	CETEC, KVC, ICONS, VTT, IDENER

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The impact of engagement activities will be analysed again in D7.9 (Second report on public engagement actions, M33) and D7.15 (Final report on public engagement actions, M47).

7. References

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- [3] A. Ostling, M. Francoli, and F. Steibel, 'From Informing to Empowering: Improving Government-Civil Society Interactions within Open Government Partnership (OGP)', 2016.